

PROBLEM-SOLVING STRATEGIES OF YOUNG CHILDREN WORKING ON A COMBINATORICS TASK IN A COMPUTER ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation: When young children are provided with a computer environment for solving combinatorial tasks, they can employ various problem-solving strategies that enhance their understanding of the concept. The trial and error method, visual representations, collaboration, immediate feedback, and scaffolding are all strategies that children can utilize in a computer environment to develop their problem-solving abilities. By engaging in interactive and visual activities, children can explore, experiment, and develop a deeper understanding of combinatorics, setting a strong foundation for their mathematical learning.

Key words: combinatorics, problem-solving strategies, cognitive abilities, systematic approach, initial observations, algorithmic thinking, complex tasks.

When young children are working on a combinatorics task in a computer environment, they may employ several problem-solving strategies. These strategies can vary depending on the individual child's cognitive abilities and prior experiences. Here are some common problem-solving strategies observe din young children:

1. Trial and error: Children may randomly try different combinations or options to see what works. They explore the possibilities and learn from their mistakes until they find the correct solution.
2. Systematic approach: Some children may take a systematic approach by organizing their thinking and trying all possible combinations one by one. They create a logical order and methodically go through each option until they find the right answer.
3. Pattern recognition: Children with strong pattern recognition skills may notice recurring patterns or relationships between different elements of the task. They use these patterns to make predictions or eliminate options, narrowing down their choices.
4. Guessing and checking: Children might make educated guesses based on their initial observations or intuitions about the problem. They then check whether their guess leads to a correct solution or not.
5. Peer collaboration: In a computer environment, children can collaborate with their peers to solve combinatorics problems together. They share ideas, discuss different approaches, and collectively work towards finding solutions.
6. Algorithmic thinking: Some children may develop algorithmic thinking skills where they break down complex tasks into smaller, more manageable steps. They follow a specific set of instructions or rules to solve each step until they reach the final solution.
7. Visual representation: Young children often benefit from visual representations of problems, such as using diagrams, charts, or images to understand combinatorics concepts better. Visual aids can help them visualize possibilities and make sense of abstract ideas.
8. Transfer of knowledge: Children who have prior experience with similar combinatorics tasks may transfer their knowledge from previous situations to tackle new problems efficiently. They recognize similarities between tasks and apply previously learned strategies or techniques.

It is important to notice that these problem-solving strategies are not exclusive, and children may combine multiple approaches depending on the specific task and their individual preferences. Additionally, as children gain experience and develop their mathematical thinking skills, they may refine and adapt these strategies to become more efficient problem solvers. Combinatorics, a branch of mathematics that deals with counting, arrangements, and combinations, can be a challenging topic for young children. However, when provided with a computer environment, children have the opportunity to explore combinatorial problems and develop problem-solving strategies in a more engaging and interactive manner.

One of the primary benefits of using a computer environment for combinatorics tasks is the ability to provide immediate feedback. When children attempt to solve a combinatorial problem, the computer program can quickly evaluate their solutions and provide feedback on the correctness of their answers. This immediate feedback helps children to identify any errors or misconceptions they may have and encourages them to revise their strategies accordingly.

In a computer environment, young children can also benefit from visual representations and simulations that aid in understanding combinatorial concepts. For example, a computer program can present problems involving arranging objects in a specific order or selecting objects from a set. Through interactive visualizations, children can see the impact of their choices and observe how the number of possibilities changes as they modify their selections. This visual feedback helps children develop a better understanding of combinatorial principles and encourages them to think critically about the problem at hand.

Furthermore, a computer environment allows for the exploration of multiple problem-solving strategies. Children can experiment with different approaches, such as systematic listing, making organized charts or tables, using diagrams, or even employing trial and error methods. By providing a digital platform that supports various strategies, children can develop their problem-solving skills and discover the most efficient and effective approaches for combinatorial tasks.

Collaboration is another significant advantage of a computer environment for combinatorics problem-solving. Children can work together on a shared computer screen, discussing their ideas, comparing strategies, and collectively finding solutions. This collaboration fosters communication skills, team work, and the ability to learn from others. Additionally, computer environments often offer opportunities for online collaboration, allowing children to connect with peers from different locations, share their approaches, and engage in discussions to deepen their understanding of combinatorial concepts.

It is worth noting that while a computer environment can enhance problem-solving experiences, it should not replace the role of the teacher. Teachers play a crucial role in guiding students, facilitating discussions, and helping them make connections between different problem-solving strategies. Teachers can also use the computer environment as a tool to assess students' understanding, provide targeted feedback, and offer additional challenges or resources to support their learning. Combinatorics, the branch of mathematics that deals with counting and arranging objects, can be a challenging concept for young children to grasp. However, when provided with a computer environment, children can develop problem-solving strategies that enhance their understanding of combinatorial tasks.

The interactive and visual nature of computer programs allows children to experiment, explore, and apply various strategies to solve combinatorial problems effectively.

One problem-solving strategy that young children often employ when working on combinatorial tasks in a computer environment is the trial and error method. By manipulating objects or variables within the program, children can see the immediate results of their actions. They can test different combinations and observe the outcomes, helping them understand the relationship between different elements in the problem. This iterative process of trial and error allows children to refine their approach and gradually develop a deeper understanding of combinatorial concepts.

Another strategy employed by young children is the use of visual representations. Computer programs often provide visual aids such as diagrams, charts, or graphs that help children visualize the problem and its possible solutions. By representing the problem visually, children can better understand the relationships between objects or variables and make connections between different components of the problem. Visual representations also facilitate the exploration of patterns, enabling children to identify regularities and develop generalizations about combinatorial tasks.

Furthermore, the use of technology allows children to collaborate and engage in problem-solving activities with their peers. Computer programs often incorporate features that enable children to work together, exchange ideas, and discuss strategies. Collaborative problem-solving fosters communication, critical thinking, and teamwork skills. By working with others, children can benefit from different perspectives and approaches, leading to a deeper understanding of combinatorial concepts.

The immediate feedback provided by computer programs is another significant advantage for young children working on combinatorial tasks. As children manipulate objects or variables, the program can provide real-time feedback on the correctness of their actions. This feedback allows children to reflect on their strategies, identify errors, and make adjustments accordingly. By receiving immediate feedback, children can develop a sense of self-assessment and self-correction, promoting metacognitive skills and enhancing their problem-solving abilities.

Moreover, computer environments often offer scaffolding features that support children's problem-solving processes. These features can include hints, prompts, or step-by-step guidance that assist children in approaching and solving combinatorial tasks. Scaffolding helps children build confidence, develop strategies, and overcome challenges they may encounter during the problem-solving process. As children become more proficient in their problem-solving skills, they can gradually reduce their reliance on scaffolding and become more independent learners.

It is fact that children were exposed to the problem over a longer period of time that influenced their outcome and not the digital version and the duo of artifacts as such? The duration of an activity was addressed by Jupri, Drijvers, and Van Den Heuvel-Panhuizen (2015). In their case, the intervention lasted for more than 5 h. However, the students in their study did not use a duo of artifacts but either a digital or a physical artifact. Their study showed that students using the digital artefact outperformed their peers using the physical artefact. Despite our much shorter intervention. We got results similar to those of their students who used the digital artefact, maybe as a result of our use of a duo of artefacts.

However, as we have not studied children who have used only the digital artefact we can only record how the digital version of the task influenced the written records in combination with a paper and pencil version of the task and not how the digital version of the task might function on its own in a different educational setting. Another possible explanation of the results in cycle 3 is the issue of proper and meaningful context when young children work on combinatorial tasks, which has been addressed by English (1991, 2005). In cycle 3 the children first were given the opportunity to make sense of the context of the task by using the digital version without an actual task being posed to them. Maybe this led to the context of the later task being more understandable when they were asked to work with paper and pencil and explain the changes shown. Even taking time and context into consideration, the duo of artefacts seems to have had impact. While being exposed to a duo of artefacts, the children made fewer duplications and more children managed to find more permutations. We argue that exposure to a possible structure contributed to this improvement. This aligns with Maschietto and Soury-Lavergne (2013) when they state that the artefacts forming the duo both have to have common characteristics and have to differ in order to improve a learning experience.

Nevertheless, it could be asked whether another paper and pencil artefact might not be as effective as this digital artefact in providing this amplification: for example, if the children had been given a sheet with 6 boxes or 6 outline drawings of bears in a row for them to colour. However in such a situation feedback regarding the concept of duplicates would not automatically come up. Further, several children had less than 6 solutions – including their duplicates – when only working with paper and pencil, indicating that providing six boxes would not necessarily have helped them. Systematic variation and constancy (English 1996) are a natural part of the digital version of the task whereas these principles are not always possible to discern when working on the task with merely paper and pencil.

When using the digital version of the task the children do not need to use systematization, but systematization is offered in the form of a structured way to look at solutions. Also the principle of completion (and consequently also the principle of exhaustion) is incorporated in the digital version, as it indicates when all permutations are found. The concept of duplications is introduced visually to The Children working with the digital version of the task while they get the opportunity to explore systematization and duplication further when working with paper and pencil. Thus, the duo of artefacts is coherent and offers both continuity and discontinuity, where the digital version makes children aware of systematization and duplication.

We are aware that such exposure would be possible with paper and pencil; however, a digital version adapts the time of such exposure to the process of the user and makes it therefore more effective. When the children later work with paper and pencil they themselves have to find a way to systematize their permutations that (hopefully) helps them to notice duplicates. The outcome of fewer duplications along with more successful solutions argues that children might have come to a better understanding.

In conclusion, a computer environment provides young children with an interactive and engaging platform to explore combinatorial problems and develop problem-solving strategies. Through immediate feedback, visual representations, multiple strategies, and collaborative opportunities, children can enhance their understanding of combinatorics and strengthen

their problem-solving skills. By integrating technology in to combinatorics tasks, educators can create a dynamic learning environment that fosters creativity, critical thinking, and mathematical reasoning in young learners.

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